
**FEASIBILITY STUDY FOR OFFERING BACHELOR OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION
IN THE ACADEMIC YEAR 2024-2025 AT GORDON COLLEGE,
OLONGAPO CITY**

Kristoffer Paul C. Obispo¹, LPT
Agnes L. Melo¹, MPA
Darwin P. Paguio¹, PhD
Ediric D. Gadia², PhD

¹*College of Education, Arts, and Sciences*

²*Research Development and Community Extension Services*

How to cite: Obispo, K.P.C., Melo, A.L., Paguio, D.P., Gadia, E.D. (2023). Feasibility study for offering Bachelor of Public Administration in the academic year 2024-2025 at Gordon College, Olongapo City. *The APO*, 6(1), 65-75. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10851561>

INTRODUCTION

Public administration is a multidisciplinary field that prepares individuals for public, private, and non-profit roles. The need for competent public administrators is increasing as the global environment becomes increasingly interconnected, complex, and challenging. According to CHED (2010), public administration prepares individuals for careers in public administration and governance for the public interest. In the same manner, the University of the Philippines- National College of Public Administration and Governance (UP-NCPAG) (UP-NCPAG, n.d.) defined the bachelor's degree in public administration to "prepare individuals in assuming positions in public service such as government agencies, international organizations, and non-government organizations." The Philippines was the first country in Asia to offer a degree in Public Administration, dating back to 1952 (Torneo, 2020). Torneo (2020) also noted that the Philippine Public Administration education has changed to reflect the nation's shifting political, governmental, and economic conditions. Spanish and American colonial influences have shaped the public administration system in the Philippines (Haque, 2013). Over time, this system has evolved, facing challenges related to leadership and identity (Cruz, 2020). Recent scrutiny of public health policies and programs in the Philippines underscores the significance of effective governance and public trust in these initiatives (Labana et al., 2020).

As society becomes increasingly complex, the need for competent and effective public administration professionals grows (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2015). Colleges in the Philippines play a crucial role in providing education and training across various fields, including public administration. Public universities and colleges, such as state universities and colleges (SUCs) and local colleges and universities, are instrumental in offering programs related to public administration (Tan, 2017).

For several reasons, offering a bachelor's degree in Public Administration at public colleges and universities in the Philippines is crucial. Firstly, establishing such programs aligns with the global trend of expanding educational opportunities in public administration

(Azizuddin & Hossain, 2020). The importance of offering specialized degrees like Public Administration is underscored by the fact that public universities play a significant role in human capital development and offer socially relevant degrees (O'Neill & Bagchi-Sen, 2022). Moreover, the need for highly qualified administrative professionals is increasing with the modernization of state governance, emphasizing the necessity for colleges and universities to provide relevant majors such as Public Administration (Dong, 2018). In light of this, universities must expand their offerings and provide programs that cater specifically to the needs of aspiring public administrators. This feasibility study aims to determine whether sufficient demand exists for offering a new program focused on a Bachelor of Public Administration (BPA) at the institution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tables and figures below summarize the results and findings of the survey conducted by the researchers.

Table 1. Profile of the respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage	
Age	16 years old	4	1.8
	17 years old	91	40.3
	18 years old	86	38.1
	19 years old	28	12.4
	20 years old	7	3.1
	21 years old	3	1.3
	22 years old	4	1.8
	23 years old	2	0.9
Sex	24 years old	1	0.4
	Female	139	61.50
	Male	87	38.50
School	Barretto Senior High School	33	14.60
	Kalalake National High School	20	8.85
	Tapinac Senior High School	43	19.03
	Mabayuan Senior High School	40	17.70
	New Cabalan Senior High School	49	21.68
	School outside Olongapo	41	18.14
Total	226	100	

The table provides information on the profile responses of individuals based on their age and sex, as well as the schools they attend.

The table shows the frequency and percentage of individuals in each age group. The majority of respondents are 17 and 18 years old, with 91 respondents (40.3%) and 86 respondents (38.1%), respectively. The number of respondents decreases as age increases, with the lowest frequency and percentage in the 24-year-old category.

Regarding sex, the table indicates the number of female and male respondents. There are 139 female respondents, accounting for 61.50% of the total, and 87 male respondents, representing 38.50% of the total.

The table also provides information on the schools attended by the respondents. It lists the names of the schools and the corresponding frequency and percentage of respondents from each school. The highest number of respondents came from New Cabalan Senior High School, with 49 respondents (21.68%), followed by Tapinac Senior High School, with 43 respondents (19.03%). The lowest number of respondents came from Kalalake National High School, with 20 respondents (8.85%).

Table 2. Responses of the Student-Respondents

Questions	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1) Do you intend to work in the government or public service until retirement?	YES	148	65.49
	NO	78	34.51
2) Do you like to serve and protect the interest and welfare of the general public?	YES	178	78.76
	NO	48	21.24
3) Do you participate in different public or civic society activities in your place?	YES	117	51.77
	NO	109	48.23
4) Are you familiar with the Local Government Code of the Philippines and its provisions or contents?	YES	100	44.25
	NO	126	55.75
5) Are you knowledgeable about technical assistance in government and civil society?	YES	106	46.90
	NO	120	53.10
6) Do you like to conduct research in the government, civil society, and academic institutions?	YES	136	60.18
	NO	90	39.82
7) Do you have experience(s) in developing managers of small and medium-sized voluntary sector or civil society organizations?	YES	79	34.96
	NO	147	65.04
8) Do you intend to apply for executive positions in the local, provincial, and national government institutions?	YES	89	39.38
	NO	137	60.62
9) Do you plan to run for local and national government elective positions?	YES	72	31.86
	NO	154	68.14
10) Do you intend to position yourself as an executive in national, regional, and international organizations?	YES	74	32.74
	NO	152	67.26
11) Are you interested in the development of managers of sizeable voluntary sector or civil society organizations?	YES	96	42.48
	NO	130	57.52
12) Do you have adequate knowledge and understanding of the fundamentals of good governance?	YES	165	73.01
	NO	61	26.99
13) Do you appreciate the demands and challenges of public service?	YES	184	81.42
	NO	42	18.58

14) Do you possess high ethical values for public service, accountability, nationalism, and sustainability?	YES	161	71.24
	NO	65	28.76
15) Do you have a strong sense of duty to promote and protect public interest, especially for the depressed and marginalized communities?	YES	156	69.03
	NO	70	30.97
16) Do you have adequate management skills, including planning, implementation, monitoring, and human, material, and resource management from government and civil society organizations?	YES	143	63.27
	NO	83	36.73
17) Do you possess adequate ability to engage in scientific research and national decision-making?	YES	121	53.54
	NO	105	46.46
18) Would you like to upgrade your current "know-how" in public service?	YES	167	73.89
	NO	59	26.11
19) Are you willing to enroll again in college and finish a degree or a short-term course for public service under a particular or modular class?	YES	136	60.18
	NO	90	39.82
20) Are you aware of a course or degree related to government or public service?	YES	171	75.66
	NO	55	24.34
Total		226	100.00

The survey collected responses from participants on various aspects of their engagement, attitudes, and intentions toward government, public service, and related activities. Here is a consolidated summary:

The majority of respondents express positive sentiments toward public service:

- 65.49% intend to work in government or public service until retirement.
- 78.76% like to serve and protect the interests of the general public.
- 51.77% participate in public or civic society activities.

However, there are mixed levels of familiarity and engagement in specific areas:

- 44.25% are familiar with the Local Government Code of the Philippines and its provisions.
- 46.90% are knowledgeable about technical assistance in government and civil society.
- 60.18% have an interest in conducting research.

The respondents also demonstrate varying degrees of experience and interest in roles:

- 34.96% have experience developing managers of small and medium-sized civil society organizations.
- 39.38% intend to apply for executive positions in government.
- 31.86% have plans to run for elective positions.

- 32.74% have an intent to position themselves as executives in organizations.

Ethical values, governance knowledge, and a sense of duty are prominent:

- 73.01% have adequate knowledge of good governance fundamentals.
- 81.42% appreciate the demands and challenges of public service.
- 71.24% possess high ethical values for public service, accountability, nationalism, and sustainability.
- 69.03% have a strong sense of duty to promote and protect public interest.

Skills and education play a role:

- 63.27% have adequate management skills, including planning, implementation, monitoring, and resource management.
- 53.54% are capable of engaging in scientific research and national decision-making. 73.89% are interested in upgrading their knowledge for public service.
- 60.18% are willing to enroll again for education in public service.

Finally, there is awareness of educational opportunities:

- 75.66% are aware of courses or degrees related to government or public service.

Respondents generally show positive inclinations towards public service and civic engagement. Their responses highlight their intentions, interests, experiences, and aspirations across various areas related to government and public service.

Challenges and Limitations in Pursuing College Education

Listed below are some of the themes that arise from the responses:

1. **Financial Constraints:** Dominant concern, with many worried about affording education costs.
2. **Educational Preparedness and Limitations:** Concerns about readiness include communication skills and academic knowledge gaps.
3. **Time Management and Responsibilities:** Challenges balancing study, work, and family.
4. **Social and Personal Challenges:** Issues like social anxiety, low self-confidence, and relationship difficulties.
5. **Uncertainty and Indecision:** Indecision about future study or career paths.
6. **Distance and Transportation:** Concerns about reaching colleges far from home.
7. **Health and Well-being:** There are a few health-related challenges affecting college attendance.
8. **Social Factors and External Influences:** Family expectations, lack of motivation, and societal influences.
9. **Ethical and Social Issues:** There needs to be more academic integrity and social equity mentions.

The primary hindrances for individuals are financial constraints, educational preparedness, and personal challenges.

Perceptions of Public Service Education Importance

Central Theme: *Emphasizing the necessity of public service education for effective governance and public administration.*

Subthemes:

1. **Addressing Skill Gaps:** Educate current officials to fill skill gaps for efficient service.
2. **Equipping Aspiring Officials:** Prepare future officials with essential knowledge and skills
3. **Enhancing Ethics:** Promote values like accountability and ethical behavior
4. **Promoting Effective Governance:** Educated officials make better decisions
5. **Empowering Community:** Increase public understanding of government roles for collaboration
6. **Catalyst for Change:** Education seen as driving positive government change

Public service education is crucial for enhancing skills, promoting ethics, and driving positive change in governance.

Positive Responses:

1. Interest in the program's content and relevance.
2. Motivated by a desire to serve the community/country.
3. Seeking personal growth and overcoming challenges.

Negative Responses:

1. Lack of interest in politics/public service.
2. I have already chosen another course.
3. Perceived program difficulty.
4. Financial constraints.
5. Specific concerns about institutions.

Neutral/Uncertain:

1. I am still deciding about college plans.
2. Conditional considerations, e.g., scholarships, job prospects.

Miscellaneous:

1. Some feedback unrelated to the course.
2. Minor grammatical and spelling errors.

Participants' willingness is influenced by their interests, career goals, financial status, and perceptions of the program and institutions. The data show that the majority are undecided. Thus, there is a need to market the program and inform students about it.

JOB OPPORTUNITIES FOR BPA GRADUATES

According to *Section 5 of CMO No. 06, a 2010 series*, the program prepares its graduates for technical and administrative positions in government, including in the Foreign Service and civil society. It is a good preparation for those interested in law. Graduates can look forward to executive and policy-making positions in government, both elective and appointive, and executive and policy-making positions in civil society organizations.

Entry-level Jobs:

- Technical assistants in government and civil society
- Researchers in government, civil society, and academic institutions
- Development managers of small and medium-sized voluntary sector or civil society organizations

Advanced Office Position:

- Executives in the national and local government institutions, including government-owned and controlled corporations
- Elective positions in local and national government
- Executives in national, regional, and international organizations
- Development managers of large voluntary sector or civil society organizations

CONCLUSION

This study comprehensively analyzes the demographic profile, sentiments, and aspirations of individuals considering a career in public administration. The survey

involved diverse respondents, comprising youth aged 17-18, with a higher female representation. Schools like New Cabalan Senior High School and Tapinac Senior High School were predominantly featured. A strong inclination toward public service was evident, with over 65% of respondents intending to work in this sector until retirement. Notably, 73.01% demonstrated a substantial understanding of good governance.

Despite general positivity toward public service, gaps exist in specific knowledge areas, such as the Local Government Code and technical assistance in government. The responses revealed a mix of hindrances in pursuing public administration, with financial constraints leading to educational preparedness and personal challenges. Perceptions of the importance of public service education were overwhelmingly positive, emphasizing its necessity for effective governance and public administration.

The data indicate market readiness and demand for a Bachelor of Public Administration (BPA) program, which aligns well with the job opportunities in government and civil society as outlined by CMO No. 06, series of 2010. The study concludes that there is substantial interest in and a crucial need for a BPA program. However, strategic marketing and financial support are needed to convert undecided prospects into enrolled students.

GENERAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results above of the feasibility study survey and the conclusion being drawn, the following are therefore recommended:

- 1) **Targeted Marketing:** Considering the high number of undecided respondents, targeted marketing campaigns should focus on the program's benefits and career prospects.
- 2) **Financial Assistance:** Given the concern about financial constraints, scholarship programs, and financial aid could attract more enrollees. They may be subjected to the FHE program since the institution is an LUC and offers a program under FHE.
- 3) **Curriculum Focus:** Given the strong inclination towards public service but moderate awareness of local laws, the curriculum could include a robust focus on governance, ethics, and local regulations.
- 4) **Skill Development:** Respondents noted the importance of skills like management and research, and skill-oriented modules can be incorporated.
- 5) **Address Challenges:** Introduce preparatory courses or workshops that address the common challenges identified, such as educational preparedness and time management.
- 6) **Engagement with High-Response Schools:** Build partnerships with New Cabalan and Tapinac Senior High School, which showed the highest number of interested students.

- 7) **Career Guidance:** Offer career guidance to illustrate the various roles and opportunities available after graduating with a BPA, thus making the program more appealing.

Reference

- Azizuddin, M. and Hossain, A. (2020). Reflections on public administration education with a case of Bangladesh. *Teaching Public Administration*, 39(1), 46-66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0144739420929372>
- Commission on Higher Education (2010). CHED Memorandum No. 06 series of 2010. Policies and Standards for Bachelor of Public Administration (BPA) Program. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CMO-No.06-s2010.pdf>
- Cruz, L. (2020). Governing the Philippine public: The National College of Public Administration and Governance and the Crisis of Leadership Without Identity. *Scientia - The International Journal on the Liberal Arts*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.57106/scientia.v9i1.116>
- Denhardt, J. V., & Denhardt, R. B. (2015). *The new public service: Serving, not steering*. Routledge.
- Dong, Q. (2018). The Innovation Model of Teaching and Human Resource Cultivation in Major of Public Administration in the Process of State Governance Modernization. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 18(6).
- Haque, M. S. (2013). Public administration in a globalized Asia: Intellectual identities, challenges, and prospects. *Public Administration and Development*, 33(4), 262–274.
- Labana, R., Nissapatorn, V., Cada, K., & Sandoval, K. (2020). A cross-sectional analysis of Facebook comments to study the public perception of the mass drug administration program in the Philippines. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.34172/ijhpm.2020.55>
- O'Neill, M. & Bagchi-Sen, S. (2022). Public universities and human capital development in the United States. *Geojournal*, 88(1), 733–751. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-022-10636-1>
- Tan, J. (2017). Factors affecting stress among faculty members of public universities in the Philippines: a multiple regression analysis. *International Journal of Psychological Studies*, 9(3), 64. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijps.v9n3p64>

Torneo, A. R. (2020). Public administration education in the Philippines 1951-2020: History, challenges, and prospects. *Journal of Public Affairs Education*, 26(2), 127-149.

University of the Philippines- National College of Public Administration and Governance (UP-NCPAG) (n.d.) Bachelor of Public Administration (BPA). <https://ncpag.upd.edu.ph/academic-programs/undergraduate-program/#:~:text=The%20Bachelor%20of%20Public%20Administration,%2Dgovernment%2C%20and%20international%20organizations.>